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Residential Bidirectional Charging Considering Vehicle to Home and Vehicle to Building

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Abstract

In this paper an optimization model for bidirectional charging of battery electric vehicles is presented. Therefore, different optimization objectives were developed. The objectives include a cost-oriented, a residual load oriented and a combined objective. These objectives were developed for a centralized and decentralized approach. The simulation results show that with a decentralized cost-based method, the load power peak of a building or district can reach a high extent, but the cost for each household is low. A decentralized residual load-oriented strategy offers a benefit for the grid together with higher costs for each household. The combined objective offers both a low cost and a benefit to the grid. The results indicate that households and districts can be powered by a photovoltaic system, a battery energy storage system and a battery electric vehicle in transition and summer period without any grid delivery. The power peak and most of the grid demand arise in the winter months. Cost-oriented strategies led to a simultaneity of the charging strategies of up to one for the battery electric vehicles. Compared to this, a combined strategy offers a benefit to the grid and only slightly higher costs and reduces the maximum power peak by 80 %. Centralized strategies can help to reduce the peak power even more compared to the combined strategy by about 63 %. All strategies have in common that the operating hours of the charging components are very high compared to the estimated lifetime of the vehicle. The mean operating hours are 1.500 hours a year with peaks of up to 3.000 hours a year.

Keywords: Bidirectional Charging, Vehicle to Home, Sustainable Energy Consumption, Electric Vehicle Charging

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation of this Research

In Germany the energy transition is stepping forward. Due to the high share of renewable energy sources and their integration into the energy system, new challenges arise, e.g., the high production peaks. These generation peaks have to be cut and surplus of energy should be stored for times with a lower production of renewable energies. Besides this, Germany wants to transform the transport sector and replace combustion

engines with zero emission vehicles. The goal for 2030 is to have 15 million electric vehicles on German roads [1]. Most of these vehicles will be battery electric vehicles (BEV). A lot of these electric vehicles will be charged at home or at work [2]. Specifically, the charging at home can cause grid stress through the high load of the electric vehicles [3]. Technical restrictions need to be applied to avoid grid overloading. An example for a such regulation is the update of German EnWG 14a law which allows the grid operator to reduce the charging power in situations in which a grid overloading is assumed, detected by measurements and grid calculations [4]. Consequently, the electric grid faces challenges by fluctuating high production of electric energy and simultaneously by a high peak demand of electric power through electric vehicles. A possible solution is the intelligent integration of BEV into the energy system by coordinated charging. The coordinated charging strategy already helps to reduce the grid stress. The BEVs potential can be fully utilized, if used as a storage system which provides grid services or sells energy in times when the renewable energy production is not sufficient to power the grid. It is also possible to store the self-produced energy from a photovoltaic (PV)-plant for a later use in the home system this use case is often named as vehicle to home, e.g. overnight as illustrated in Figure 1. Another use-case is the optimization of the energy purchase by profiting from dynamic electricity tariffs.

Figure 1: Illustration of the vehicle to home use case

Most of the research is focusing on the provision of ancillary services and the increase of self-consumption of the self-produced PV energy. In this paper the possibility of the reduction of the sizing of stationary battery storage system (BESS) due to the possibility of vehicle to home charging will be shown. This effectively increases the usage rate of the infrastructure without negative effects on the lifetime and helps to increase the profitability of the system. Also, strategies to decrease the peak demand using a coordinated bidirectional centralized control system will be shown. These can help to decrease the simultaneity of the charging processes without negative effects on the customer side. The developed centralized strategies could be used in energy communities or in multi-family houses. The centralized strategies will be compared to decentralized strategies with the same goal of power peak reduction and their benefits are carried out.

1.2 Structure of the Paper

In chapter 2 related work is analysed and differentiated from this work. Here, it is focused on German energy research but also some selected international research is analysed. In chapter 3, the developed optimization model which forms the basis of this work is presented. In chapter 4, the used data, their sources and characteristics are introduced. Moreover, the created simulation scenarios are presented. Thereafter, in chapter 5, the results of this research are shown and analysed. In chapter 6, the outlook and further evaluations are carried out. In chapter 7 a conclusion of this research is drawn.

2 Related Research

In [5] different charging strategies for electric vehicles and their impact on the grid are analyzed. It is focused on the optimization possibilities for the grid operation and the planing of real world low voltage grids. The charging strategies consider variable grid fees, bidirectional charging with the goal for self-consumption increase and the optimization of the energy prices based on a dynamic energy tariff on household basic. Peak shaving is only used for households with a consumption over 100.000 kWh. In this research different centralized strategies are applied and compared to also applied decentralized strategies.

In [6] different grid-serving strategies are presented, which are focussing on the impact on the future energy system and their benefit to the grid. The positive impacts for the future energy system are carried out. But like [5] the focus is only on decentralized strategies.

Nevertheless all this research has in common, that only the different operating hours of the used components are analysed, neglecting the aging of the components. Also the impact on the customer is not adressed nor considered.

Also, they do not analyse the relation between a BEV and the BESS. This relation will be considered in this work and the impact of a BEV on the possible reduction of the BESS size is carried out.

3 Methodology

In section 3.1 the developed optimization models are explained. In section 3.2 the constraints of the corresponding objective functions are shown while all power flows in the household are modelled to analyse all power flows. Section 3.3 explains the procedure of the executed simulations and the used framework.

3.1 Introduction of the different Objective Functions

Within this section, the optimization model is presented. Three different objective functions with two different spatial levels of observation, one on single-household level and one on a multi-family house level, are described. The first objective function, Formula 1, aims for minimizing the costs of electricity use within the household. This function can be divided into two parts. The first part represents the costs of energy procurement from the grid which are calculated by the power from the grid ($P_{Grid}(t)$) multiplied by the time-dependent energy costs ($C_{Grid}(t)$). The second part of the formula represents the time-dependent earnings of the PV system through the feed-in of energy ($P_{Sell}(t)$). Here, the earnings E_{Sell} are static values. The goal of this objective is to minimize the result.

$$\min \sum_t^T [(P_{Grid}(t) \cdot C_{Grid}(t)) - (P_{Sell}(t) \cdot E_{Sell})] \quad (1)$$

The second objective function of the optimization model aims to reduce the maximum grid power and thus generate the lowest possible peak for the grid see formula 2. For this purpose, the individual residual powers are squared in order to incentivize small values, as these have less impact on the total.

$$\min \sum_t^T P_{Grid}(t)^2 \quad (2)$$

The third objective function aims to combine the first two objective functions and is extended by imaginary penalty cost (C_{Peak}) for the highest power peak in the optimization period.

$$\min \sum_t^T [(P_{Grid}(t) \cdot C_{Grid}(t)) - (P_{Sell}(t) \cdot E_{Sell}) + \max(P_{Grid}(t)) \cdot C_{Peak}] \quad (3)$$

These described three objective functions are used on household level for a decentralized optimization. For central optimization considering energy community or multi-family house level, the objective functions are modified. Therefore all households are optimized together. Every building includes the sum of all

households. The first objective aims to reduce the cost for the complete building with objective in Formula 4. These optimized cost are not necessary the lowest costs for every user itself.

$$\min \sum_{t,h}^{T,H} [(P_{Grid}(t,h) \cdot C_{Grid}(t,h)) - (P_{Sell}(t,h) \cdot E_{Sell})] \quad (4)$$

The goal of the second objective of the centralized perspective, Formula 5, is to reduce the power peak of the complete complex.

$$\min \sum_{t,h}^{T,H} P_{Grid}(t,h)^2 \quad (5)$$

The third objective, see Formula 6, in the building perspective aims to find the best possible point between these two objectives. Therefore, the same approach like for the household basis is used.

$$\min \sum_{t,h}^{T,H} [(P_{Grid}(t,h) \cdot C_{Grid}(t,h)) - (P_{Sell}(t,h) \cdot E_{Sell}) + \max(P_{Grid}(t,h)) \cdot C_{Peak}] \quad (6)$$

3.2 Constraints of the Optimization

Besides these objectives different constraints were used. In the following the constraints are introduced. For a better understanding the constraints are only shown for the household basis. In the objectives for the multi family home the constraints only have the different household in the constraint added alike the objective functions.

All variables are used as positive values. So the lower bound of every variable is zero. Some variables have an upper bound based on the used scenario. Every power flow in the household and building was modelled which results in a lot of different constraints and makes the optimization model quite complex.

The BESS is restricted through the following two constraints. The first constraint is only valid for the first timestep of the optimization to include a start state of charge (SOC) of the BESS ($SOC_{BESS}(t)$) which is multiplied by the capacity of the BESS ($Capacity_{BESS}$). $P_{BESS}(t)$ represents the charging power of the BESS. $P_{Discharge,BESS}(t)$ is the discharging power. η_{BESS} is the efficiency of the charging and discharging action of the BESS.

$$E_{BESS}(t) = SOC_{BESS}(t) \cdot Capacity_{BESS} + [P_{BESS}(t) \cdot \eta_{BESS}] - \left[P_{Discharge,BESS}(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_{BESS}} \right] \quad \forall t = 1 \quad (7)$$

For all other timesteps the $SOC_{BESS}(t)$ is replaced by the energy content of the prior timestep shown through $E_{BESS}(t-1)$. This results in the constraint shown in Formula 8.

$$E_{BESS}(t) = E_{BESS}(t-1) + [P_{BESS}(t) \cdot \eta_{BESS}] - \left[P_{BESS,Discharge}(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_{BESS}} \right] \quad \forall t \in \{2,3,\dots,T\} \quad (8)$$

The charging power of the BESS (P_{BESS}) consists of power from the PV-plant ($P_{PV,BESS}$) and the power from the electric vehicle $P_{BEV,BESS}$. And a switch variable to avoid a charging and discharging in the same timestep. $Switch_{BESS}$ is a binary variable. This results in Formula 9.

$$P_{BESS}(t) = (P_{PV,BESS}(t) + P_{EV,BESS}(t)) \cdot Switch_{BESS} \quad \forall t \quad (9)$$

The restriction for discharging of the BESS is quite similar. With the sum of all power flows to the different components see Formula 10.

$$P_{BESS,Discharge}(t) = (P_{BESS,Load}(t) + P_{BESS,BEV}(t) + P_{BESS,Grid}(t)) \cdot (1 - Switch_{BESS}) \quad \forall t \quad (10)$$

The modelling of the BEV is alike the model of the BESS. The energy content is calculated based on an initial $SOC_{BESS}(t)$. The charging and discharging power consists of the sum of the power flows to the different components. One difference to the BESS is the addition of a switch to allow charging only when the car is at home ($Switch_{BEV,home}$). An other different addition is a constraint for the minimal ($P_{BEV,min}$) and maximum charging power ($P_{BEV,max}$). The model consists of the Formulas 11-16. An important factor is to fulfill the energy requirement of the BEV. This is modelled through the Formulas 17 and 18 where $E_{BEV,Charged}$ represents the required energy through mobility behavior of the BEV.

$$E_{BEV}(t) = SOC_{EV}(t) \cdot Capacity_{BEV} + [P_{BEV}(t) \cdot \eta_{BEV}] - \left[P_{BEV,Discharge}(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_{BEV}} \right] \forall t = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$E_{BEV}(t) = E_{BEV}(t-1) + [P_{BEV}(t) \cdot \eta_{BEV}] - \left[P_{BEV,Discharge}(t) \cdot \frac{1}{\eta_{BEV}} \right] \forall t \in \{2,3, \dots, T\} \quad (12)$$

$$P_{BEV}(t) = (P_{PV,BEV}(t) + P_{BESS,BEV}(t) + P_{Grid,BEV}) \cdot Switch_{BEV}(t) \cdot Switch_{BEV,home}(t) \forall t \quad (13)$$

$$P_{BEV,min}(t) \leq P_{BEV}(t) \leq P_{BEV,max}(t) \forall t \quad (14)$$

$$P_{BEV,Discharge}(t) = (P_{BEV,Load}(t) + P_{BEV,BESS}(t)) \cdot (1 - Switch_{BEV}(t)) \cdot Switch_{BEV,Home}(t) \forall t \quad (15)$$

$$P_{BEV,min}(t) \leq P_{BEV,Discharge}(t) \leq P_{BEV,max}(t) \forall t \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_t^T P_{BEV}(t) \cdot \eta_{BEV} = E_{BEV,Charged} \forall t \in \{start_charging, \dots, end_charging\} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_t^T P_{BEV}(t) \cdot \eta_{BEV} = 0.0 \forall t \in \{end_charging, \dots, start_charging\} \quad (18)$$

Another implemented constraint is to avoid an acquisition and a simultaneously feed-in of energy through a Switch ($Switch_{Grid}$) which is implemented in the constraint for the acquisition (P_{Grid}) and feed-in of energy (P_{Sell}). This constraint is shown in Formula 19 and 20.

$$P_{Grid}(t) = (P_{Grid,EV}(t) + P_{Grid,Load}(t)) \cdot Switch_{Grid}(t) \forall t \quad (19)$$

$$P_{Sell}(t) = (P_{BESS,Sell}(t) + P_{PV,Sell}(t)) \cdot (1 - Switch_{Grid}(t)) \forall t \quad (20)$$

The power flow from the PV-plant is modelled through the individual power flows to the other Components. This is shown by Formula 20.

$$P_{PV}(t) = P_{PV,BESS}(t) + P_{PV,Sell}(t) + P_{PV,BEV}(t) + P_{PV,Load}(t) \forall t \quad (21)$$

Also, the required load of the household itself has to be fulfilled by the different elements. This requirement is represented through Formula 22.

$$P_{Load}(t) = P_{PV,Load}(t) + P_{BEV,Load}(t) + P_{BESS,Load}(t) + P_{Grid,Load}(t) \forall t \quad (22)$$

3.3 Procedure of the Simulations

The Gurobi solver is used to solve the optimization problems. In this work a rolling optimization was used. Therefore, first an optimization was executed to determine a suitable SOC for the BESS and the BEV as the initial SOC of the BESS is zero and may not be a suitable starting point for the optimization due to different seasons. The initial SOC for the BEV is read-in from data series generated by [7] which does not use optimizations. This can lead to an implausible SOC at the start of the Optimization because it could be possible that the optimization would shift the charging times to a later time. Using this approach, a caused inaccuracy of these shifted times is minimized. An optimization time period of two weeks was chosen. The end of the first week determines the start of the next, the second optimization. At the end only the first week of the second optimization was evaluated to avoid inaccuracy because of the complete discharging of the BEV and the BESS at the end of the optimization time. In decentralized methods the time limit was set to 1000 seconds per optimization cycle and the time limit for the central strategies were set to 41600 seconds. Due to long optimization times only one optimization for one week of each season is executed. Therefore, three periods summer, winter and a transition period which represents autumn and spring were analyzed. An optimization of a whole year would have taken many runtime of the different optimizations. Afterwards the results of each season are scaled to one year to determine the variation to a simulation of one year.

4 Data and Parameters of the Optimization

In section 4.1 the used data and their sources are introduced and the characteristics of this data is shown. Afterwards the fixed parameters of the simulations are presented in section 4.2.

4.1 Used Data and Datasources

Different load, generation and electric vehicle profiles serve as input parameters for the optimization. The generation profiles are based on real data of a PV-plant at the elenia institute of the TU Braunschweig and are scaled to different sizes. The load profiles are generated from [8] and the electric vehicle profiles are generated with [7]. The vehicle profiles are created based on different mobility behaviors. Therefore, a distinction is made between full-time workers, part-time workers and leisure users[7]. In this paper the focus is only on driving profiles of a full-time worker. The mobility behavior of the BMW i3 is approximately 6.000 km a year with driving range of 137 km (17.8 kWh) in the winterweek, 97 km (18.6 kWh) in the summer week and 117.1 km (25.2 kWh) in the transition period. The mobility behavior of the ID.3 is about 9.000 km with 148 km (29.3 kWh) in the winterweek, 238 km (33.0 kWh) in the summer week and 155 km (22.7 kWh) in the transition period. Besides these different vehicle profiles, different PV-systems in terms of pv power production and battery size were used. The production for the used week is 2.8 kWh in the winterweek, 34.2 kWh in the summer week and 28.9 kWh in the transition period per kWp resulting in the given PV production. Although the loadprofiles of the household were divided into four different profiles. These different distinctions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Different used parameters of the optimization

PV production per year	Loadprofiles	Battery energy storage	Battery electric vehicles
6.2 MWh	1-person profile	2 kWh	BMW i3 (33 kWh)
9.8 MWh	2-person profile	4 kWh	VW ID3 (45 kWh)
13.6 MWh	3-person profile	6 kWh	
16.0 MWh	4-person profile	8 kWh	

4.2 Constant Parameters of the Optimization

In addition to the selected parameters, other necessary parameters are set to constant values (see Table 2). In this paper, the efficiencies for charging and discharging of the battery storage system and the electric vehicle were set to fixed values. Also different minimum charging rates for electric vehicles were used. The minimum SOC of the BEV is set to 20 % as a safety reserve to take unplanned mobility into account. A maximum

charging rate of 11 kW was assumed because it is a typical charging power for home charging in Germany. The simulation step size is set to 15-minutes, as it is a common standard for energy system analysis. The peak power price is based on the mean of peak power prices in Germany [13]. But in this case the peak power price is spread evenly over the complete year and scaled to one week.

Table 2: Constant parameters of the simulation

Parameter	Value
Charging und discharging efficiency BEV and BESS	0.95 [9]
Maximum charging and discharging rate BESS	0.5 C
Safety reserve of the BEV	20 % SOC
Minimum charging and discharging power BEV	1.4 kW [10]
Maximum charging and discharging power BEV	11 kW
Fixed energy costs	12.38 Cent/kWh [11]
Fixed feed-in price	7.65 Cent/kWh [12]
Time step	15 Minute
Peak power price	2.10 €/kW

5 Results

In the following selected simulation results are shown and analysed. This chapter is divided into two parts. In section 5.1 the results of the decentralized strategies are shown. In section 5.2 the results of the centralized strategies are shown.

5.1 Results from the decentralized strategies

In Figure 2 the relation between the costs and the battery size of the households is shown. Each boxplots includes 32 different configurations. It is shown that the range of the boxplots differs for every size. But the mean value is only slightly different between the battery sizes from 185.67 € to 225.63 € per year. This is caused by the different energy demand of each household and the constraint for the minimal charging power of the BEV. Because of this constraint energy has to be transferred from the BEV to the BESS all the time which causes losses through two different charging processes. Still, it is clearly shown that bidirectional charging can reduce the size of the BESS to optimize the use of the infrastructure.

Aggregating all these households to one district or a multifamily house result in a simultaneity factor of 1 for the BEV charging processes. This is due to the low PV production in the winter, where all cars are charged at the same time at the lowest possible costs. In summer and in the transition period nearly all required charging energy can be procured by the PV-plant. Either by the direct use of the PV power or by stored PV energy in the BESS or BEV. The power peak occurs in times with a low demand of the household itself, because the peak for the loads is about 57 kW besides the aggregated peak of 347 kW with a peak of 341 kW due to the electric vehicles. This peak is equal over all battery sizes.

Figure 2: Relation between costs and battery size for different configurations

In Figure 3 the relation of the operating hours of the BEV dependent on the battery size is shown. It is visible that a smaller battery leads to higher operating hours of the BEVs. The reasons for this effect are the shift of energy from the BEV to the BESS and this causes higher losses. The mean value of all these configurations is about 1500 operating hours. If this mean value is compared to the normal lifetime of a vehicle approximate with about 8.000 hours [14], this results in about 1/6 of guaranteed operating hours of a vehicle over lifetime in only one year. But in some configurations the operating hours are even higher and can reach up to 3.000 hours. Because of this the automotive industry has to adjust its requirements for the components involved in the charging and discharging process for an effective roll-out of bidirectional charging.

Figure 3: Operating hours for the BEVs dependent on the BESS size

In addition, the cost-based objective function causes a high power peak. This can lead to a necessary expansion of the grid and therefore to an increase of the grid fees which results into higher costs for the customer. The second objective function aims to avoid this problem.

With this objective function the power peak of the aggregated households can be reduced to 25 kW if all households own an 8 kWh BESS. If all households own a 2 kWh BESS it can only be reduced to 39.6 kW. Besides this it has to be mentioned that the time limit was set to 1000 seconds for each household and in some households this time limit was reached resulting in some not-optimal solutions. So, there may be some more optimization potential. This load peak shaving leads to an increase of the costs for the individual households. Where the mean values of the different battery sizes are shown in Table 3. The average additional costs are 80 € per household compared to the cost-oriented strategy.

Table 3: Mean costs for the different battery sizes with the peak objective

Battery size	Mean costs
2 kWh	307.73 €
4 kWh	283.44 €
6 kWh	268.52 €
8 kWh	261.49 €

In Figure 4 in the self-sufficiency rate for the different season is shown. It is shown that in the transition and summer period nearly the whole energy can be drawn from the PV, BESS or the BEV. But in the winter period the production of the PV is not high enough to fulfill the demand. Also, the power peak occurs in the winter period with 60 kW compared to 26 kW in the transition or summer period depending on the BESS.

Figure 4: Boxplot of self-sufficiency rate based in the season

In Table 4 the results for the combined objective are shown. It is visible that the power peak can be reduced up to 80 % with only little more costs compared to the cost objective. These higher costs are caused through the shifting of the energy from the BEV to the BESS. This shifting is necessary through the minimum charging power of the BEV. These results do not include cost for the power peak this part of the objective was only used to incentivize lower power peak.

Table 4: Results of the combined function

Battery size	Mean costs combined objective	Difference to cost objective	Power peak
2 kWh	258.52 €	+ 32.90 €	135 kW
4 kWh	225.96 €	+ 23.22 €	110 kW
6 kWh	209.69 €	+ 18.49 €	89 kW
8 kWh	203.74 €	+ 18.08 €	71 kW

5.2 Results from the centralized strategies

In this section only the results of the combined strategy are shown. The peak objective was not able to find a suitable solution because of the high number of different constraints with the mentioned time limit. The objective for the cost optimal solution was not used because from the decentralized results it was already visible that these objective leads to high power peak.

In Table 5 the results of the centralized combined objective are shown. It is visible that the power peak can be further reduced by about 63 % compared to the decentralized strategy. The mean costs are in the same area like the cost objective for the decentralized objective. The slight differences between the different battery sizes are caused through the rolling optimization because some energy can be delivered in a different time slot which is not integrated in the calculation. The power peak only slightly derives between the configurations through the dominating peak power price and through some not optimal results.

Table 5: Results of the centralized combined objective

Battery size	Mean costs combined objective	Power peak
2 kWh	187.32 €	50 kW
4 kWh	186.51 €	50 kW
6 kWh	184.75 €	51 kW
8 kWh	187.14 €	51 kW

6 Outlook and Further Evaluations

In future work variable efficiencies based on the current charging power of the BEV and the BESS will be integrated. Current literature respectively the underlying measurements have shown that the charging power has a high impact on the efficiency and can increase the accuracy of the simulations. [9, 15, 16]

Another aspect which is neglected in the current form of the model are costs for the battery degradation through bidirectional charging. The literature has not agreed on this factor. Literature like [17] show a high decrease degradation of the battery but others like [18] show in some selected operating points only a slight impact on the battery health.

Also, the combined objective will be used with different weighting factors to see the sensitivity of the different price elements it was visible in the centralized strategies that the peak power price is dominating.

In the future, these optimization results will be used to execute grid calculations. Also, it is planned to build an optimization model which integrates results from the grid calculation like line loading, workload of the transformer, voltage at the grid connections point and other aspects to offer a benefit to the grid.

At the current state of the optimization, the electric vehicle user is not incentivised for his grid-serving measures. So, the user would not adjust his strategies to avoid grid overloading. Therefore, incentives for the user to behave in grid-serving manner will be developed and tested within the optimization model.

Another aspect to investigate is the influence of different regulations on bidirectional charging, e.g. the German EnWG 14a law.

7 Conclusions

The simulation results show that bidirectional charging offers a lot of benefits to the user. When applying a realistic minimum charging power of 1.4 kW, the BEV cannot fully replace a BESS to power the household. When combining BEV and BESS, it is possible to power the house without drawing energy from the grid in summer and in the transition period. Nevertheless, in the winter months it is still necessary to draw energy from the grid. Cost-based charging strategies can lead to high power peaks and a possible simultaneity factor of 1. This can cause grid overloads as the grids were originally not designed for these charging processes. A possible solution which integrates a peak power price was shown. This strategy reduced the power peaks by up to 80 % by only slightly higher costs for each household. Another solution to reduce the power peaks was shown by the centralized charging strategies. An additional reduction of the power peak by 63 % compared to the decentralized combined strategy was shown. And the cost were quite similar to the cost optimization results. Due to bidirectional charging, the operating hours of the involved components are rising up to 3.000 hours a year. This should be considered when developing the next generation of BEVs.

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